

Progress Report: DAPHNE Use Case

Dynamics in Correlated Electron Systems. Inelastic x/n Scattering

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Abstract

We present recent progress in the "Dynamics in Correlated-Electron Systems" use case within the DAPHNE consortium (DATA from PHoton and Neutron Experiments), funded by the German National Research Data Infrastructure (Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur, (NFDI e.V.)). DAPHNE aims to enhance the transparency and FAIRness (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability) of data obtained from photon and neutron facilities, making it more accessible to the broader research community beyond the originating experimental groups. To achieve this, we are developing dedicated metadata vocabularies for inelastic neutron scattering and inelastic x-ray scattering techniques and promoting the use of electronic laboratory notebooks. These efforts are integrated with a new scientific data catalogue and remote data analysis platform at the Heinz Maier-Leibnitz Zentrum (MLZ), designed to streamline and improve the documentation and analysis of experimental workflows.

Figure 1: FAIR data lifecycle of neutron triple-axis spectrometer (TAS) experiments at MLZ, illustrating the workflow from proposal submission and data collection through documentation, storage, evaluation, and publication.

1 Introduction

Inelastic scattering is a critical tool for investigating lattice dynamics and magnetic excitations, playing a pivotal role in materials science and condensed matter research. Traditionally associated with neutron studies, advancements in modern synchrotron radiation facilities opened up new avenues for obtaining comparable, and often complementary, inelastic X-ray scattering data, essential for many cutting-edge scientific inquiries. This includes experiments conducted under high-pressure, on tiny single crystals and/or on strongly neutron-absorbing materials.

Inelastic neutron scattering (INS) and inelastic x-ray scattering (IXS) experiments are conducted at large-scale facilities, such as nuclear reactors and spallation sources for neutron production and synchrotron radiation facilities and free electron lasers for intense x-ray beams. Scientists submit their beam time application (or proposals) and time on a given instrument is allocated via a peer-review system. Typically, many more proposals are submitted than can be allocated, and the system is, thus, competitive. Since experiments cannot be repeated easily, the importance of comprehensive documentation pertaining to these datasets is critical. Each dataset necessitates a thorough collection of metadata to support future (re-)analysis.

2 A typical user-driven neutron scattering experiment at MLZ

The Heinz Maier-Leibnitz Zentrum (MLZ) is Germany’s leading neutron research facility and one of the world’s foremost centers for advanced research using neutrons and positrons. As a user facility, MLZ offers an extensive portfolio of high-performance instruments that support a wide range of scientific disciplines, including structural analysis, spectroscopy, imaging, elemental characterization, nuclear and particle physics.

MLZ operates a dedicated data management strategy tailored to the specific requirements of neutron instrumentation and complex data workflows. The standard research data lifecycle begins with the submission of a proposal via the Garching Online System Tool (GhOST, <https://ghost.mlz-garching.de>), which collects essential administrative metadata such as the principal investigator (PI), experiment details, requested instrument, and initial sample information.

Following peer review and approval, researchers travel to MLZ to carry out their experiments. The facility ensures that measured data is reliably acquired and stored on disk for a defined period of time. MLZ systematically preserves data and associated metadata about instrument configuration, operational status, calibration, and sample environment parameters. This is complemented by user provided information on sample preparation, prior characterization, and any user-supplied equipment.

A typical Triple-Axis Spectroscopy (TAS) experiment—one of the most established methods in neutron spectroscopy—proceeds in a well-defined manner. Prior to arrival, researchers have already specified the scientific objectives, planned sample orientation, and a feasible instrument configuration as part of the proposal process. Upon arrival, the team mounts and aligns their sample, usually a single crystal, on the TAS instrument, such as PUMA, using known Bragg reflections. The experiment is carried out by adjusting instrument parameters such as neutron energy, collimation, monochromator and analyzer angles, and sample environment conditions like temperature or magnetic field. A schematic of the PUMA spectrom-

eter is shown in Figure 2, highlighting the primary beamline, sample table, and secondary spectrometer arm, including analyzer and detector components optimized for high-resolution inelastic neutron scattering.

Description:

- ① Variable slit / virtual source
- ② Collimators [automatic changing $\alpha_1, \alpha_2,$
- ③ Monochromator [automatic mono changing]
- ④ Sample table
- ⑤ Analyzer single & multi (11 fold)
- ⑥ Detector single & multi (11 fold)
- ⑦ Analyzer and detector housing

Operated by

Figure 2: Schematic of the thermal triple-axis spectrometer PUMA, operated by the Technische Universität München (TUM) and Karlsruher Institut für Technologie (KIT) at MLZ. The instrument consists of a primary beamline section (1–3), a sample table (4), and a secondary spectrometer arm (5–7), including analyzer and detector components, optimized for high-resolution inelastic neutron scattering.

Data collection is conducted via the NICOS instrument control system (www.nicos-controls.org), which manages scan sequences and stores key instrument metadata in the raw data files. While NICOS captures many critical parameters automatically, researchers typically keep parallel records in personal notebooks or local digital files. These records often include notes about sample alignment, scan rationale, configuration changes, unexpected events, or complementary observations. Because this documentation is decentralized, varies in structure, and may not always be preserved with the data, it can be challenging to reconstruct the full context of an experiment at a later time, especially for collaborative or long-term projects.

Currently, once an experiment is complete, raw data and limited metadata are stored on MLZ servers and are accessible for a fixed retention period. Any further structuring, annotation, or sharing of this data is handled manually by the user group. There is no standardized mechanism in place to consolidate experiment logs, user observations, and metadata across instruments and proposals. This can make data difficult to revisit, share, or reuse, especially when considering long-term reproducibility or FAIR data principles.

To address these challenges and streamline the documentation and data management process, two key digital services are being developed within the DAPHNE4NFDI initiative: the MLZ Electronic Laboratory Notebook (MLZ-ELN) and the SciCat data catalogue. The MLZ-ELN will provide a structured, searchable, and collaborative digital environment for real-time experiment documentation. It will integrate with NICOS and the user office system, allowing metadata to be captured automatically while enabling users to supplement it with text notes, sketches, images, and structured observations. This will significantly reduce the burden on users and ensure that contextual information is preserved alongside the data.

In parallel, the SciCat data catalogue will offer a centralized system for dataset registration, indexing, and retrieval. It will collect metadata from GhOST, NICOS, and the ELN, assign persistent identifiers (PIDs), and provide search and filtering tools to facilitate data discovery and reuse. Together, the MLZ-ELN and SciCat represent a major improvement over the current workflow by enabling consistent metadata capture, improving traceability, and supporting a FAIR-compliant data lifecycle from proposal to publication.

3 The status of metadata capture and electronic laboratory notebooks before DAPHNE at MLZ

Before the initiation of the DAPHNE project, metadata capture and electronic laboratory notebook (ELN) infrastructure at MLZ existed in a fragmented state. While the facility ensured reliable data acquisition and storage during experiments, metadata practices varied considerably across instruments and user groups, often relying on local conventions and non-standardized formats.

Measured data were stored on-site and retained for a defined period of time, but comprehensive metadata about the experiment, such as instrument configuration, sample environment conditions, calibration parameters, and contextual information provided by users, were often dispersed across multiple systems. These included instrument control system logs (e.g., NICOS), digital or paper laboratory notebooks, spreadsheets, and embedded metadata in data files. Such heterogeneity made it difficult to enforce consistent documentation practices, automate data processing pipelines, or support long-term data reuse.

The standard workflow at MLZ began with users submitting a proposal through the GhOST. This system collected key administrative and bibliographic metadata, such as investigator details, requested instruments, and basic information about the samples. After the proposal was reviewed and approved, users would conduct their experiments on-site. While certain metadata (e.g., instrument settings and motor positions) were logged automatically by the control system during data collection, much of the contextual and procedural information remained user-dependent and was often recorded manually.

Experiment execution, short-term data storage, and initial processing took place within the MLZ infrastructure. However, responsibility for long-term data archiving—including the proper organization and documentation of datasets—rested primarily with the users. Although MLZ could provide support upon request, the absence of centralized, machine-readable, and standardized metadata workflows limited the overall effectiveness of these efforts.

In summary, prior to DAPHNE, MLZ had a solid foundation for experiment execution and local data storage, but lacked integrated solutions for metadata standardization, provenance tracking, and FAIR-compliant (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) data management. This highlighted the urgent need for unified metadata schemas and the adoption

of ELNs to enhance reproducibility, transparency, and collaboration in neutron scattering research.

4 Work program of use case spectroscopy/dynamics in correlated electron systems

The DAPHNE4NFDI consortium is dedicated to enhancing the FAIRness (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability) of data generated at photon and neutron research facilities. Our specific use case, focusing on spectroscopy and dynamics in correlated electron systems, leverages all task areas of the DAPHNE4NFDI project. We place particular emphasis on Task Area 1 (TA1): Managing Data Production, which aims to develop tools and best practices for comprehensive data and metadata capture throughout the experimental lifecycle.

4.1 Objectives within Task Area 1

Our use case addresses several key components within TA1:

- **Metadata and Vocabulary Specification:** Defining and standardizing metadata schemas and vocabularies pertinent to INS and IXS experiments. This ensures consistent documentation of experimental parameters, sample information, and data processing steps.
- **Online Logbook Integration:** Implementing and integrating Electronic Laboratory Notebooks (ELNs) to facilitate real-time documentation of experimental workflows, observations, and metadata capture. ELNs serve as centralized platforms for recording experiment-related information, enhancing data traceability, reproducibility, and machine-readability.
- **Automatic Metadata Capture:** Developing tools and protocols for the automated collection of metadata directly from instrument control systems and data acquisition software. This minimizes manual entry errors and ensures the completeness and accuracy of metadata records.
- **Standard High-Performance Data Formats:** Adopting and promoting the use of standardized data formats, such as `NeXus`, to facilitate data interoperability and ease of analysis across different platforms and research groups.

4.2 Alignment with the DAPHNE4NFDI FAIR Data Lifecycle

The activities in our use case are structured to align with the FAIR data lifecycle (Figure 3) as delineated by the DAPHNE4NFDI consortium. This lifecycle encompasses the stages of data generation, processing, analysis, preservation, and sharing, ensuring that data remains FAIR throughout its existence.

Figure 3: DAPHNE4NFDI FAIR Data Lifecycle for Photon and Neutron Sources. This schematic illustrates the stages of data management, from proposal submission to data reuse, highlighting the integration points for ELNs and metadata capture tools [1].

In practice, our use case contributes to this lifecycle by:

- **Enhancing Data Findability:** Through standardized metadata and centralized documentation in ELNs, data sets become more discoverable by both humans and machines.
- **Improving Accessibility:** By integrating ELNs with data repositories and adopting common data formats, we facilitate easier access to data for authorized users.
- **Ensuring Interoperability:** Standardized vocabularies and data formats enable seamless data exchange and integration across different research infrastructures and analytical tools.
- **Promoting Reusability:** Comprehensive metadata and documentation support the understanding and reuse of data sets in future research, fostering new insights and discoveries.

4.3 Implementation and Testing

We are already actively testing our tools and approaches on the virtual instruments and infrastructure available at MLZ — an opportunity that allows us to simulate and evaluate metadata workflows in a realistic yet controlled environment. This early-stage deployment provides valuable insights that inform ongoing development. In the next phase, we plan to extend testing to real experiments conducted on collaborating beamlines. These practical applications will deliver critical feedback to refine our solutions and ensure they meet the needs of researchers in neutron and X-ray spectroscopy.

5 Progress on Metadata standards and vocabulary specification

We co-author the metadata white paper [2] and provide the detailed use case *Neutron Triple Axis and Extended X-ray Absorption Fine Structure Spectroscopy*. The developed metadata dictionaries are used to develop and implement a SciCat data catalogue (, Task Area 2 (TA2)) at MLZ. An effort to establish detailed metadata of other neutron scattering instruments is ongoing.

The suite of spectrometers at MLZ currently includes eleven instruments, several of which are under construction. Within the first funding phase of the DAPHNE project, our focus has been directed toward the triple-axis spectrometer (TAS), which serves as a representative case among the broad spectrum of instrumentation and methodologies applied in neutron spectroscopy. TAS is characterized by its user-oriented data acquisition process, typically yielding structured output in human-readable ASCII format. However, the instrument's high degree of configurational flexibility and its broad scientific applicability necessitate the capture and management of a complex and diverse set of metadata.

To address these requirements, we have developed dedicated metadata dictionaries for INS, with a particular emphasis on TAS instruments. Our proposed metadata schema includes specifications for:

- A standard (unpolarized) neutron triple-axis spectrometer setup, where incident and scattered neutron energies are selected using sets of crystal monochromators, and experiments are primarily conducted on single-crystal samples.

We defined a set of metadata that can be generically used for the inelastic spectroscopy, including the information for typical samples, that we consider necessary for future use and reuse. The metadata categories presented here are based on the recommendations published in the metadata white paper [2], which is available to the research community. While these categories are intended to support a broad range of neutron and photon experimental techniques, this summary demonstrates their application specifically to neutron triple-axis spectroscopy.

Detailed tables containing all proposed metadata fields and their definitions are provided in the Metadata White Paper [2]. The proposed metadata categories are summarized in Table 1. For TAS-specific examples and field recommendations, we refer to the Appendix. These guidelines support standardized metadata capture and promote data reuse, provenance tracking, and interoperability across user facilities.

Table 1: Summary of proposed metadata categories for neutron scattering experiments, including descriptions and representative examples. These categories support standardized data documentation, aiding in data management, reuse, and interoperability across user facilities.

Metadata Category	Description	Examples
Bibliographic / Administrative Data	Supports identification, attribution, and management of experiments across facilities and over time.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Instrument ID: PUMA@FRM II, EIGER@PSI • Proposal Number: Facility-assigned experiment number • Experiment Team / PI Name: Names and affiliations
Data Set	Describes how, when, and under what conditions the data was acquired.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Start and End Time: Timestamps for measurement or scan • Scan Type: Constant-Q, constant-E, Q-E • Sample Environment Conditions: 10 K, 3 T field, etc.
Sample	Details the physical, chemical, and crystallographic properties of the investigated sample.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sample ID: FeSe_42 • Chemical Composition: BaFe₂As₂ • Crystal Orientation / Alignment: (H, 0, L) • Sample Dimensions: 5 mm × 20 mm cylindrical
Record of Experiment Conduction	Documents how the experiment was performed, including instrument configuration and settings.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monochromator and Analyzer Settings: PG(002), energy resolution, mosaic • Fixed Final Energy (E_f): 14.7 meV • Collimation and Filters: PG filters, pre-/post-sample collimation • Motor Positions and Scan Ranges: Goniometer or detector angles logged per scan

6 Progress on Electronic Laboratory Notebooks

6.1 ELN White Paper

In collaboration within TA1, we established a comprehensive list of ELN requirements for neutron and X-ray experiments at PaN user facilities, as presented in the ELN White Paper [1]. This specification set, covering technical capabilities, usability, and integration features, guides the selection of appropriate ELN software tailored to the needs of a specific facility, institute, or instrument.

The ELN White Paper outlines the strategic and technical considerations necessary for evaluat-

Figure 4: Information flow from data generation and experiment control into an ELN. Modern ELNs support both manual input via web interfaces and automated ingestion through APIs, enabling seamless integration with instrumentation [1].

ing ELN solutions suited to the unique demands of PaN research infrastructures. As experimental environments in this field become increasingly data-intensive and collaborative, the need for ELNs capable of integrating seamlessly with facility workflows and managing large volumes of structured metadata has grown substantially.

Figure 4 illustrates a typical information flow from the experiment and instrument control systems into an ELN. In modern ELN implementations, this process involves both human interaction through a web interface and automated data ingestion via application programming interfaces (APIs). This schematic highlights the central role of ELNs in capturing metadata at the point of generation and supporting real-time collaboration and data integrity in complex experimental environments.

Key features that support these requirements are listed in Table 2 and include parallel editing capabilities, user authentication and access control, and automated data ingestion through APIs. Parallel editing, for instance, allows multiple users, often located at different institutions or beamlines, to simultaneously contribute to a shared experiment logbook without overwriting each other’s input. This is crucial for enabling collaborative beam times and remote participation, where real-time updates from different locations are essential.

Similarly, user authentication and access control are vital to ensuring that only authorized individuals can access, edit, or manage specific parts of the ELN. This functionality is typically implemented through integration with institutional identity systems and role-based permissions, which protect data integrity and enforce project-specific privacy requirements. These features work together to create a secure, collaborative environment for researchers, ensuring both the privacy of sensitive data and the efficiency of teamwork.

The White Paper defines a structured set of ELN specifications, ranked by importance, to guide the evaluation of potential ELN solutions. The specifications emphasize the need for scalability to accommodate the growth of facility-wide deployment and ensure that these systems can handle large volumes of data and metadata efficiently.

Table 2: Essential specifications for Electronic Laboratory Notebooks (ELNs) at large-scale photon and neutron (PaN) research facilities, as defined in the ELN White Paper [1]. These features, marked with the highest importance level (3/3), are considered critical for enabling secure, collaborative, and FAIR-compliant documentation workflows in data-intensive experimental environments.

Specification	Description	Examples
API Access	Application programming interface to allow automatic data ingestion and remote interaction with ELN content.	Instrument-generated metadata, experiment logs via RESTful API.
Intuitive Use	A user-friendly interface that supports efficient navigation and editing.	Modern web GUI with structured input forms and rich-text editing.
Reliability	Ensures integrity and traceability through versioning and audit trails.	Change history, immutable records, digital timestamps.
Open Source	Source code is openly available for review, adaptation, and community contributions.	Public repositories (e.g., GitHub).
Documentation	Availability of user documentation, tutorials, and developer guides.	User manuals, onboarding guides, API documentation.
Content Export	Export of entries in standard formats for archiving and reuse.	PDF, HTML, JSON.
Parallel Editing	Multiple users can edit or contribute to the same entry simultaneously.	Collaborative beam time logging.
Authentication	Secure user identification based on institutional or federated credentials.	Single Sign-On (SSO), Helmholtz AAI.
Authorization	Role-based access control to regulate permissions.	Differentiated access for PI, instrument scientist, guest user.
Searchable	Full-text and metadata-based search across all entries.	Tag search, filter by user or instrument, keyword-based retrieval.
Scalable	Designed to support concurrent users and instruments at facility scale.	Central ELN for all instruments at MLZ.
Image Import	Support for importing standard image files from local or cloud sources.	Setup photos, scanned handwritten notes, sample images.
Server Deployment	Can be centrally deployed and maintained at research infrastructure level.	Facility-hosted on-premises instances with backup support.

Specification	Description	Examples
Free-form Input	Support for rich-text content, embedded media, and styled documentation.	Notes with tables, figures, text formatting, equations.
Recovery	Mechanisms for data backup and restoration.	Auto-backup, version restore, disaster recovery tools.
Auto Save	Automatic saving of entries to prevent data loss.	Live-save during entry or sensitive sessions.

To facilitate the comparison of different ELN systems, the White Paper introduces an evaluation methodology based on a figure of merit (Pn), which allows ELN candidates to be quantitatively assessed against the defined specifications. This enables objective comparison, supports transparent decision-making, and helps align selected solutions with both technical and user requirements.

The framework has been applied to several ELN systems evaluated within the DAPHNE4NFDI consortium, including those in use or development at MLZ, EuXFEL, and other PaN facilities. These case studies demonstrate how the specification-driven approach supports effective ELN selection and sustainable integration into complex research environments.

6.2 ELN Evaluation and selection at MLZ

Following the specification-driven approach outlined in the ELN White Paper, we conducted a systematic evaluation of several open-source ELN solutions to identify the most suitable system for deployment at MLZ. Given the unique operational context of MLZ as a research reactor facility, where diverse instruments, frequent collaborations, and strict data integrity requirements converge, it was essential to select an ELN capable of integrating well with our workflows and meeting a broad set of technical and usability criteria.

Using the specification framework and figure of merit (Pn) methodology, each ELN candidate was assessed against the ranked requirements, including features such as API-based data ingestion, user authentication, structured metadata support, and facility-wide scalability. This structured process enabled an objective and transparent comparison of available options.

While some solutions demonstrated strong performance across many key areas—particularly in integration readiness, usability, and open-source development—a critical feature emerged as a determining factor in the final selection: the ability to support parallel editing. This functionality is especially important for collaborative beam times and remote participation, where multiple users may need to interact with the same experiment logbook simultaneously. As this requirement could not be met adequately by the systems initially considered, the search was extended to alternative solutions that better aligned with the collaboration-focused workflows at MLZ.

Ultimately, the TUM-based software WORKBENCH (<https://www.ub.tum.de/workbench>) was selected as the foundation for the MLZ-ELN solution. Developed at the Technical University of Munich (TUM), Workbench is a universal research data and project management platform designed to support collaboration and semi-automated documentation. Recognizing its flexibility and extensibility, it was chosen as a basis upon which a more tailored ELN system for neutron experiments at MLZ could be developed.

As a neutron and X-ray spectroscopy group, we contributed actively to shaping the MLZ-ELN. Drawing on the ELN specifications defined within TA1, we proposed essential adaptations and extensions, and continue to support the development by testing the software on the virtual TAS PANDA instrument at MLZ. Our testing includes functionality assessments, usability feedback, and debugging, all aimed at creating an efficient and user-friendly interface for documenting neutron scattering experiments.

The current focus is to ensure that the MLZ-ELN will integrate seamlessly with the local instrument and software infrastructure. This includes enabling direct data input from the instrument control system, user authentication and role-based access control, and providing an intuitive, web-based interface for researchers. In the next phase, the MLZ-ELN will be deployed in real experiments, with initial trials planned for the PUMA spectrometer.

Despite its initial promise, it soon became clear that the ELN component of Workbench was relatively underdeveloped, having previously been only a small part of the overall platform. To adapt it to the specific workflows and FAIR data requirements of neutron experiments at MLZ, substantial development work was required, particularly in redesigning both the front-end and back-end architecture. This work was carried out by our software development team, led by Josef Baudisch, whose efforts extend beyond the scope of our group’s use case and contribute to the broader infrastructure development at MLZ within TA2 of the DAPHNE4NFDI project. The scope of the redevelopment was significant: the back-end of the ELN component has been completely rewritten, to the extent that the resulting MLZ-ELN can now be considered an independent system, rather than a derivative of the original Workbench platform. Through this targeted development, the MLZ-ELN is being refined to meet the specifications outlined in the White Paper [1], ensuring it supports both best practices in data management and the collaborative, data-intensive workflows characteristic of large-scale neutron experiments.

6.3 MLZ-ELN

The MLZ-ELN is currently under development to support users across the wide range of neutron instruments available at the MLZ. The ELN is integrated with NICOS, the standard instrument control system used at MLZ, and receives metadata from GhOST, the user office software responsible for managing proposals, peer review, and beam time allocation. By linking to these systems, the ELN enables the automatic recording of experiment-related information, significantly simplifying logbook maintenance.

A key feature of the MLZ-ELN is its ability to automatically capture instrument readings, experimental parameters, and summary information of the measurements, aligning with the core ELN specifications summarized in Table 2. As nearly all neutron instruments at MLZ are operated via NICOS, this integration ensures that data is consistently and accurately documented. NICOS has recently been extended, also as part of the DAPHNE initiative, to support automated data transfer to the ELN, reducing the risk of manual errors and improving efficiency.

The development of the MLZ-ELN also places a strong emphasis on collaborative work. It offers parallel editing capabilities and incorporates a robust and flexible role-based model for authentication and authorization, ensuring both usability and secure access control for scientific teams.

The structure of the MLZ-ELN is centered around discrete elements called “Notes”, as illustrated in Figure 5. These Notes can contain either instrument-generated content, such as scan information provided automatically by the control system, or user-generated content, such as comments on experiment procedures or preliminary analysis. This organization allows flexible documentation of neutron experiments by combining automated metadata capture with personalized user input.

Access rights and read/write/delete permissions are controlled through a role model, the specifics of which are still under discussion. Given the complexity and sensitivity of this matter, a detailed description will be provided once a consensus has been reached at MLZ. The backend currently under development is designed to support different models, offering flexibility in configuring user permissions based on policy decisions. Features such as versioning, track changes, and history are included to ensure data integrity and transparency.

Figure 5: Screenshot of the MLZ-ELN user interface, showing a combination of instrument- and user-generated Notes. The NICOS-generated Note at the top displays a scan summary with relevant instrument parameters in tabular form. Below, various user-generated Notes illustrate the system’s flexibility: users can enter rich text, insert tables, import images, and create sketches.

6.3.1 Instrument-Generated Notes

The content and structure of NICOS-generated Notes are planned to be instrument-specific, allowing tailored documentation suited to the unique characteristics of each experimental setup at MLZ. This concept is currently being developed and tested using a triple-axis neutron spectrometer (TAS) as a demonstration case. In the future, it is planned to extend this approach to a broader range of instruments available at MLZ.

At present, NICOS can automatically transmit basic scan metadata, short scan summaries, and sample or experiment information to the ELN. This integration is illustrated in Figure 6, which shows how specific parts of the NICOS output correspond to automatically generated entries in the ELN. Panel a) presents the NICOS interface, where a user has executed a scan and received the resulting output. Panel b) displays the corresponding ELN screen, where two Notes, highlighted in purple, were automatically created from the NICOS output. This visual mapping demonstrates how experiment control and logging are interconnected to streamline documentation and reduce the burden on users.

Users can also manually select and send specific outputs, such as data plots, to the ELN. These are not transferred automatically, but only upon user request.

Figure 7 illustrates this process: a data plot with a corresponding fit is manually selected from the NICOS interface and transferred to the ELN, where it appears as an instrument-generated Note. The ELN further enables users to annotate such images directly, adding sketches or text overlays on top of the plot for better documentation. These visual edits enhance the clarity of the record while preserving the original content, which is stored as a vector graphic (*.svg) and remains available for download or restoration.

Furthermore, any part of the NICOS output can be highlighted and sent directly to the ELN, giving users flexibility in what information is documented.

To prevent clutter and maintain a clear, human-readable logbook, users are provided with a toggle feature to control the visibility of NICOS-generated Notes. This function is available either as a checkbox ‘Auto-hide content in electronic log’ in the NICOS interface or via a dedicated NICOS

Figure 6: Example illustrating the connection between NICOS output and MLZ-ELN entries. Example illustrating the connection between NICOS and the MLZ-ELN. Panel a) shows the NICOS interface, where a user has executed a scan and obtained the corresponding output. Panel b) displays the MLZ-ELN interface. Purple rectangles in both panels represent the matching parts of the NICOS output and the automatically generated ELN entries. This visualization demonstrates how data and metadata from the instrument control system are transferred directly into the electronic logbook.

Figure 7: This example illustrates how a user can manually select and transfer a data plot with a corresponding fit from the NICOS interface to the MLZ-ELN. Panel a) shows the NICOS screen where the data plot is generated. Panel b) displays the ELN interface with the same plot inserted as an instrument-generated Note. The ELN allows further interaction with the image: users can annotate directly on top of the plot by sketching or typing text, enabling richer documentation. Purple rectangles in both panels highlight the matching content across NICOS and ELN.

command. Importantly, this feature does not delete or block data; instead, it hides selected entries from the ELN interface, ensuring that only the desired information is displayed while maintaining full data availability in the background.

6.3.2 User-Generated Notes

In addition to the automatically created entries, the MLZ-ELN offers researchers the ability to create user-generated Notes, providing flexibility and personalization to the electronic logbook. These Notes are essential for complementing the automated metadata with context-specific information, reflections, and interpretations that may not be captured by the instrument control system.

Users can insert a wide variety of content types into their Notes (see Figure 5), including:

- **Rich text:** Descriptions, comments, and experimental steps can be entered using a simple and convenient text editor.
- **Tables:** Useful for organizing measurement results or summarizing experiment conditions.
- **Images:** Photos, screenshots, or figures can be uploaded via drag-and-drop or copy-paste actions.
- **Graphs:** Plots and diagrams generated by external tools can be added for better illustration of findings.
- **Sketches:** A built-in drawing tool allows for freehand annotations, helpful for visual explanations or planning.

Each user- and instrument-generated Note can be commented on by collaborators, facilitating discussion directly within the logbook. Notes can also be positioned either inline or "aside" to help structure the ELN in a more logical and visually accessible manner. This flexibility supports collaborative workflows, allowing multiple users to contribute insights without compromising the clarity of the documentation.

In the ongoing development, particular attention is given to role-based access control, ensuring that visibility and editing rights for Notes can be tailored according to user roles (e.g., local contact, principal investigator, experimentalist). This role model will enable fine-grained permissions for reading, writing, and deleting content, an essential aspect for both data integrity and collaborative convenience.

6.3.3 Current Functionality and Features of the MLZ-ELN

While the MLZ-ELN remains under active development, many of its core features have already been implemented and are currently undergoing testing. Below is an overview of the main components and capabilities available in the current system:

- **Manual Data Input**

- **Multi-source input:** Users can enter information into the ELN from various devices and interfaces. Manual data entry is supported via any browser-enabled device. Users can also import images using built-in or connected cameras and input sketches using portable tablets.
- **Parallel input:** A critical feature for large, collaborative user groups, including remote participants, is the ability to input data simultaneously. The system supports real-time collaboration through write locks and live-reload functionality, which prevent overwriting of entries by multiple users.
- **User-friendly interface:** The ELN features a clean, intuitive interface that simplifies note creation and editing. Users can add new Notes, comment on existing ones, insert thumbnails or screenshots, and draw sketches. The integrated text editor includes essential formatting options similar to common office applications. Copy-paste of both text and images from external sources is fully supported.

- **Automated Data Ingestion from Instruments**

MLZ employs the NICOS network-based control system to operate neutron instruments. NICOS includes a built-in service for sending messages and graphically rendered outputs directly to the ELN. This automation significantly enhances experimental documentation while minimizing errors associated with manual data entry.

- **User and Access Management**

- **Role-based security model:** User access, permissions, and data ownership are managed through a flexible role model. This approach ensures both data security and collaborative efficiency.
 - **Single sign-on integration:** The MLZ-ELN integrates with Keycloak for secure single sign-on (SSO), enabling users to access data in a streamlined and secure manner.
- **User Experience**
 - **Collaborative features:** Multiple users can contribute to and comment on Notes.
 - **Change tracking and version control:** All edits are tracked, and previous versions can be restored as needed.
 - **Backup:** Regular backups ensure data persistence and recovery.
 - **Search and tagging:** Notes and entries can be tagged, annotated, and searched using full-text queries.
 - **Export:** Data can be exported in commonly used formats such as PDF, JSON, and ELNFileFormat for long-term archiving or sharing.
 - **Remote Access**

The MLZ-ELN is accessible from any device, at any time, via the web. This ensures seamless access during experiments and supports remote collaboration across facilities and time zones.

7 Outreach and dissemination

To disseminate and popularize the ideas of the FAIR data, we have presented our work at various national and international scientific conferences and meetings.

References

- [1] P. Jordt et al. “Specifications for Electronic Laboratory Notebooks (ELN) in the Photon and Neutron Community”. In: *Synchrotron Radiation News* 37.6 (2024), pp. 3–8. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08940886.2024.2432265>.
- [2] W. Lohstroh et al. *DAPHNE4NFDI — Draft recommendations on metadata capture and specifications*. Zenodo. 2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12169110>.

Appendix

To support the development of standardized metadata practices within the DAPHNE4NFDI consortium, we refer to the draft recommendations outlined in the *DAPHNE for NFDI Draft Recommendations on Metadata Capture and Specifications* [2]. These recommendations aim to ensure consistent metadata collection and support FAIR-compliant (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data workflows across photon and neutron research facilities. The following tables summarize the proposed metadata categories, which are based on two representative use-case examples considered in the project: Triple-Axis Spectroscopy (TAS) and Extended X-ray Absorption Fine Structure (EXAFS). While the first columns of the tables provide a generic structure applicable to both techniques, the last column in the **Dataset** and **Sample** tables includes specific examples that might be relevant for TAS, EXAFS, or both techniques.

Bibliographic / Administrative Data

Metadata Field	Type	Comment
Principal Investigator / Co-Proposers / Experimental Team		
Last Name		
First Name		
Email		
Affiliation		
Organization ID	ROR ID	
User ID	ORCID / Researcher ID	
Role	e.g. Principal Investigator / Experimental Conduction / Data Analyst / Sample Preparation / Support Laboratory Personnel / Local Contact / Other	
Instrument / Beamline		
Name		
Instrument PID	PID	PID of instrument or publication describing the state of the instrument at the time of measurement
Operator	Organization ID	Operator of the beamline, might be different from the facility
Facility		
Name		
Organization ID	ROR ID	of the facility where the measurement was done
Facility Contact		Functional email, e.g. data steward
Proposal		
Proposal Name		
Proposal Description		
Proposal / Experiment Identifier	Proposal ID	e.g. Proposal Identifier
Start Time	Date	Allocated Dates of Scheduled Experiment
End Time	Date	Allocated Dates of Scheduled Experiment
Public Research	Public or proprietary	

Funding Identifier		
License	e.g. CC0, CC-BY, CC-BY-SA	according to the data policy of the facility
Expiry of Embargo Period	Date	according to the data policy of the facility

Dataset

Metadata Field	Type	Comment	Usecase example
Identifier	uuid		
Identifier/Name	data set name	human readable name	
start time	Data/time	of the measurement/run: Applies to file	
end time	Data/time	of the measurement/run: Applies to file	
Sample ID	PID of sample	PID (external or local ID)	
Data format		ideally NeXus format is used	
Title/Description	free text, describing the scan		if applicable
Instrument: Configuration used, installed options	Keywords of free text	Description of installed options and links to any further information on the used instrument setup	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Single or multi-analyzer/ detector system - Monochromator type: PG(002), Ge(311), Si(111), Si(111), ... - Focusing mode: 'flat', 'horizontal', 'vertical', 'double', ... - Analyzer type: Ge(311), PG(002), ... - Scattering sense: (-1, 1, -1) (mono, sample, ana) - Collimation
Measurement technique(s)	PaNET ontology	if possible or free text	'inelastic neutron spectroscopy', 'neutron scattering', 'neutron diffraction', 'x-ray absorption spectroscopy (including EXAFS and x-ray absorption near edge structure (XANES))', 'x-ray diffraction', 'x-ray fluorescence'
Environment conditions/Settings	Key value pairs 'name, value, unit'	as many key value pairs (or time-log series) as needed, also for automatic data processing and analysis, e.g. Temperature, pressure, sample-detector distance, used wavelength, energy, beam parameter	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - "Ei": Initial energy Ei for constant ki mode, value, meV - "Ef": Final energy Ef for constant kf mode, value, meV - "ki": Initial wavevector ki for constant ki mode, value, Å⁻¹ - "kf": Final wavevector kf for constant kf mode, value, Å⁻¹ - "constE": constant Energy transfer E (Q-scan), value, meV - "constQ": constant momentum transfer Q (E-scan), vector, r.l.u. - Electric field vector in reciprocal space, vector, V/m - "element": Chosen target element for analysis, value, a.u. - "absoEdge": specific absorption edge analyzed, value, a.u. - "maxkRange": upper limit of the wavevector (k) considered during the analysis of the EXAFS oscillations, value, Å⁻¹ - "eResolution": energy resolution for EXAFS scan, value, eV

Measurement Mode	keyword	Identifying the free variable that is varied during the scan or measurement: EnergyScan, TemperatureScan, WavelengthScan, Snapshot, TimeScan, Magnetic-FieldScan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - constant Q scan with fixed ki, - constant Q scan with fixed kf, - constant E scan with fixed ω (rocking scan), - constant E scan with fixed Q/ω (longitudinal scan), ... - TOTAL ELECTRON YIELD: energy scan capturing surface electron emission as energy varies. - FLUORESCENCE: energy scan measuring x-ray induced fluorescence for bulk analysis.
Sample environment: installed options	Choice of different sample environment options by keyword, or free text, sample environment PID if available		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - polarization analysis (separate discussion) - slits (Positions and Openings) - magnet - electric Field device - pressure Cell - cryostat - high temperature furnace
Purpose of data set	choose one of: measurement, calibration / sample / background / alignment / ...		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - measurement - background - alignment - CALIBRATION
References	e.g. calibration data		link to calibration data, link to logfiles, link to instrument control logbook, link to jobfiles or measurement scripts, publications, links to pictures of mounted sample, ...
Comments	free text: to add comments after the measurement (e.g., to note mistakes, failures, etc.)	can also be provided by Nicos via the Remark() function	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Scan command: <code>qscan((0, 0.46, 0, 0), (0, 0, 0, 0.025), 18, kf=1.3, mon1=6*mpmp)</code>, - ‘measurement during cooling’, ‘temperature was rising’, ‘sample fell down’, ‘shutter was closed’, ...
Quality Metrics / Validation Status	free text	Data Quality Metrics is a number given by the user to rate the dataset.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Temperature unstable, - sample was moving, - bad data, ...

Sample

Metadata Field	Type	Comment	Usecase example
Name - human readable	free text	human readable name	
Local ID		Local ID	
ext PID	link		e.g. IGSN
registration schema		if externally registered	
Agency		if externally registered	
key words		following e.g. PhySH	examples might be: keywords similar to paper (more is better): e.g. vanadate, hermatit, iron phosphate, superconductivity, helimagnet, ... (see also PhySH.org)
Description	free text	Description of sample	
Chemical composition		e.g. CAS number, SMILE, or InCh	NiO, ZnCr ₂ Se ₄ , ...
Common name		if applicable, free text	
State	liquid, powder, single crystal, solid, thin film, in situ		liquid, powder, single crystal, solid, thin film, pressed pellet, ...
Mass	value, unit pair	if applicable	mass (g)
Crystal structure		if applicable	space group number according to IUCR
Sample Size (along crystal axis, approximate is fine)	vector	if applicable	sample volume (mm ³)
Unit cell parameters	vector	if applicable	vector $[a, b, c]$ (Å), vector $[\alpha, \beta, \gamma]$ (deg)
Preparation date	Date	if applicable	
Supplier / creator	free text	if applicable	supplier, crystal grower at institution, natural, ...
Relationships	Parent sample ID	if applicable	link to related samples (e.g. parent / child relations), datasets, ...
additional fields	free text	any additional information	sample mosaic, twinning